

Authoritarian Parenting, Emotional Intelligence and Aggressive Behavior in Students Who Have Been in Demonstrations

Riska Anggraini

Faculty of Psychology, Gunadarma University, Depok

E-mail: *riskaanggrainips43@gmail.com*

Abstract

The study aims to measure whether there is an effect of authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence on aggressive behaviour in students who have participated in demonstration activities with 109 participants. The aggressive behaviour scales uses the aggression questionnaire, the authoritarian parenting style questionnaire and the emotional intelligence scale. The results of this study indicate the influence of authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior in students who have participated in demonstration activities where authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence both have an influence on aggressive behavior. The results show that the authoritarian parenting variable has the greatest influence.

Keyword: Aggressive behavior, authoritarian parenting style, university student, emotional intelligence

1. Introduction

Nowadays, acts of violence can occur anywhere, anytime and by anyone. These actions can be in the form of verbal violence such as swearing or physical violence such as hitting and so on. Aggressive behavior also occurs within a group such as mass rallies or demonstrations. As recently, there were demonstrations carried out by students that ended in chaos due to various factors. Demonstrations certainly have their own rules that must be obeyed. But when there is a provocateur, it usually makes the demonstrators provoked so that they become anarchist and aggressive behaviors occur. Usually, this aggressive behavior can develop in students as demonstrators because of the frustration obtained during the demonstration where they have not received a response from the party being demonstrated. As stated by Sarwono & Meinarno (2009) that frustration occurs because there is an obstruction or prevention of efforts to achieve certain goals.

In addition, the presence of provocateurs is also one of the factors that are crucial in the occurrence of aggressive behavior. During a demonstration, there will be a possibility that students are provoked by emotions and experience frustration so that they trigger aggressive behaviors such as injuring or damaging, injuring or damaging an object that is around to get attention because there is no response from the party being demonstrated. At that time, the sensitivity to a cue they get will increase and tend to trigger negative things like many provocateurs do. This is caused by a decrease in self-control where individual strength will be defeated by group strength, so that some students who carry out demonstrations will focus on external events, which then creates aggressive behavior that leads to anarchist actions (Prasyatiani, 2013).

Aggressive behavior is a motive that is present in the life of every individual, although its intensity, quality and manifestation may differ from one individual to another. The low level of aggressiveness in some students lies largely in education and parenting. In early adolescent development, the family is the most important environment. The style or way of parenting each parent in educating their children is different. There are parents who want to discuss or be open in any case to their children and there are also parents who do not want to discuss or are closed in any

case to their children (Agunadi, 2017). One of the most dominant forms of parental treatment that can affect individual attitudes is a harsh way of parenting and the absence of warmth between parents and children or what is commonly referred to as an authoritarian parenting style. This type of parent is uncompromising and communication is usually one-way. This type of parent does not require feedback from their child to understand their child's intentions and wishes. But on the other hand, a person's emotional intelligence also affects aggressive behavior.

A person's emotional intelligence is formed since childhood, the process of achievement is greatly influenced by the socio-emotional conditions of the environment, especially the family environment and peer groups. If the environment is quite conducive, in the sense that it is characterized by an atmosphere of harmony, mutual respect, and full of responsibility, the individual tends to be able to achieve emotional maturity well (Yusuf, 2011). Therefore, emotional intelligence is also one of the factors that influence aggressive behavior (Luthfiani, 2017). According to Goleman (1996) emotional intelligence is a person's ability to regulate his emotional life with intelligence, maintaining emotional harmony and expression through skills of self-awareness, self-control, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills. During adolescence, this is the period where everyone often experiences what is called a self-identity crisis, so often if at this time failing to find it can have fatal consequences in the following period or when this period is being carried out.

The results of research from Cruz, Linarez, and Arias (2014) also reveal that there is a relationship between authoritarian parenting styles and aggressive behavior. Authoritarian parenting is a potential threat to adolescent adjustment in the environment such as interactions with peers. In research from Moghaddam, Asli, and Taravatmanesh (2016) also showed that authoritarian parenting can lead to aggressive behavior. The best parenting style is authoritative parenting where parenting can reduce aggression because authoritative parenting tends to emphasize independent behavior but remains friendly and gives children freedom while still within reasonable limits.

The results of research from Cruz, Linarez, and Arias (2014) also revealed that there is a relationship between authoritarian parenting style and aggressive behavior. Authoritarian parenting is a potential threat to adolescent adjustment in the environment such as interactions with peers. In research from Moghaddam, Asli, and Taravatmanesh (2016) also showed that authoritarian parenting can lead to aggressive behavior. The best parenting style is authoritative parenting where parenting can reduce aggression because authoritative parenting tends to emphasize independent behavior but remains friendly and gives children freedom while still within reasonable limits.

The results of research from Kaya, Hazar, Beyleroglu, Sari and Yilmaz (2017) indicate a relationship between emotional intelligence and aggressive behavior, where the lower a person's emotional intelligence, the higher the aggressive behavior. In addition, Masoumeh, Mansor, Yaacob, Talib, and Sara (2014) state that high emotional intelligence may be a protective factor for mental and physical health and low emotional intelligence will affect individuals with problematic behavior. This finding is in accordance with the results obtained by Kimiaei (in Masoumeh, Mansor, Yaacob, Talib, and Sara (2014) who showed that there is a significant negative correlation between emotional intelligence and aggression in adolescents where there is a significant disagreement between adolescents' emotional capacity and their problem behaviors, such as verbal aggression and behavioral aggression. It seems that people who are plagued by aggression will be weak in emotional intelligence.

Based on the explanation that has been explained, the researcher is interested in conducting research to test whether there is an influence of authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior in students who have carried out demonstrations.

2. Research Methods

This study is a case study involving 109 students who had carried out demonstrations as participants with male and female gender (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2023).

The measuring instrument of this study uses Buss and Perry's (1992) scale which consists

of 10 items. One example of this item is “Sometimes I feel that I cannot hold my anger well” This scale uses a Likert scale where there are four answer choices ranging from very appropriate, appropriate, inappropriate and very inappropriate. the results of the discrimination power of the items carried out on aggressive behavior obtained two invalid items, namely item 6 and item 8. The reliability of the scale used was 0.813 where the score showed fairly good reliability.

The authoritarian parenting measuring instrument uses a scale from Robinson, Mandelco, Roper & Hart (1995) which consists of 10 items. One example of this item is “My parents will punish me in order to discipline me, even if it means physical reprimand (such as hitting, slapping, etc.)”. This scale uses a Likert scale where there are four answer options ranging from very appropriate, appropriate, inappropriate and very inappropriate. Based on the results of the item discrimination test conducted on the authoritarian parenting measuring instrument, it is known that there are no invalid items. The reliability results on the authoritarian parenting scale show a fairly good score of 0.918.

In accordance with the research objectives, namely examining the effect of authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior in students who have conducted demonstrations, the data analysis technique of this study uses multiple regression with the SPSS version 22.00 application.

3. Results

Data collection in this study used google form. After collecting 109 participants, with female and male gender, researchers tested the effect. Researchers use multiple regression with the SPSS application. The following results have been obtained:

Table 1. Regression Test Results of Emotional Intelligence and Authoritarian Parenting on Aggressive Behavior

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	19.513	3.713		5.255	.000
1 Emotional intelligence	-.128	.061	-.190	-2.097	.038
Authoritarian parenting	.448	.064	.639	7.057	.000

Based on the results of multiple regression analysis, it shows that the results of the significance coefficient of emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior are 0.038 and the results of the significance coefficient of authoritarian parenting with aggressive behavior are 0.000. The results conducted to see the effect of authoritarian parenting on aggressive behavior show that the F value is 167.755 and the significance coefficient is 0.000 ($p \leq 0.050$). This means that the hypothesis that reads “There is an influence of authoritarian parenting on aggressive behavior in students who have done demonstrations” in this study is accepted. The R square value shows 0.613. This means that authoritarian parenting affects aggressive behavior by 61.3%, while other influences are influenced by other variables that cannot be explained in this study.

The results also show that the results of simple regression analysis which shows an F value of 87.463 and a significance coefficient of 0.000 ($p \leq 0.050$). This means that the hypothesis that reads: “There is an influence of emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior” in this study is accepted. It can be seen that the R square value is 0.452. This means that emotional intelligence has an influence on aggressive behavior by 45.2%.

The results of further analysis that the significance of the regression between authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior in this study is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), this means that there is a significant influence of authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior towards students who have participated in demonstrations. The R square value obtained is 0.628. This means that authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence in this study

have an influence of 62.8% on aggressive behavior in students who have participated in demonstrations. The results can be seen in the following table:

Table 2. The Effect of Authoritarian Parenting and Emotional Intelligence on Aggressive Behavior

F	Sig	R Square
88.767	0.000	0.628

The results of the analysis in this study indicate that two minor hypotheses are accepted and the major hypothesis in this study is accepted. This means that authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence both have an influence on aggressive behavior.

4. Discussion

In this study, the authoritarian parenting variable has the greatest influence. Parents who apply authoritarian parenting will emphasize a child's compliance with the rules they make without much explanation to the child about the reasons for the enactment of these rules, tend to punish their children who break the rules or violate applicable norms. Parents with authoritarian parenting believe that the hard way is the best way to educate their children. However, this understanding makes from the child's side, the child will imitate the education provided by his parents related to the ways of applying the rules, how to behave, and the impact of punishment in the future, will make the child affected to follow this attitude, so that if the parents are harsh, then the child will also tend to be harsh. So that from the example of a tough attitude, children tend to imitate this behavior, so that the child will behave aggressively. Starting from this parenting from childhood, which will shape children and influence them until their adulthood (Einstein and Indrawati, 2016). This is in line with research from Masud, Ahmad and Cho (2019) which shows the results of the influence of authoritarian parenting on aggressive behavior.

Another influence is emotional intelligence, emotional intelligence has a role in aggressive behavior. Alimoradi, Asadi, Asadbeigy, and Asadniya (2014) say that aggressive behavior can be reduced and reduced with good emotional intelligence. Thus, emotional intelligence has an influence on individual aggressive behavior, the higher the individual's emotional intelligence, the lower the aggressive behavior that occurs. In this case, Alimoradi, Asadi, Asadbeigy, and Asadniya (2014) also state that it returns to the role of parents who are indeed very instrumental in helping someone train their emotions so as to create good emotional intelligence where it can reduce the habits of aggressive behavior. This is in line with research from Bibi, Saleem, Khalid, and Safique (2019) which shows the results that emotional intelligence can be a factor that affects certain aspects of aggressive behavior. Therefore, proper management must be developed to improve various dimensions of emotional intelligence which will then inhibit aggressive behavior.

Based on the data of this study, authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior in students who have participated in demonstrations is 62.8%, so it is possible that there are other factors that also have an influence on aggressive behavior that cannot be seen by researchers.

5. Conclusion

The results of the analysis in this study indicate that three minor hypotheses are accepted and the major hypothesis in this study is accepted, namely "the influence of authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence on aggressive behavior in students who have participated in demonstrations". This means that authoritarian parenting and emotional intelligence both have an influence on aggressive behavior where parenting plays the most role in aggressive behavior.

From this research, it can be seen that the role of parenting in the formation of a person both from behavior, emotional intelligence and others where it will certainly shape and influence adolescence, adulthood to throughout the development of an individual. Therefore, it is hoped that readers, especially prospective parents or parents, will reconsider the right parenting style to be applied to children. For future researchers, it is expected to look more broadly at other variables that may have an effect on aggressive behavior. The variables in this study can also be a reference for future researchers to make similar studies with different subjects so that later it will further enrich readers' knowledge.

6. Bibliography

- Agunadi, R. (2017). *Angka kenakalan remaja meningkat 10% lebih*. Diakses dari <https://www.wonosobozone.com/angka-kenakalan-remaja-meningkat-20/#> pada tanggal 29 Juli 2019.
- Abdi, A. (2019). *KPAI: 24 Kasus anak disekolah pada awal 2019 didominasi kekerasan*. Diakses dari <https://tirto.id/kpai-24-kasus-anak-di-sekolah-pada-awal-2019-didominasi-kekerasan-dg8o>. Pada tanggal 29 Juli 2019.
- Afolabi. (2017). Indigenous Emotional Intelligence scale: development and validation. *Psychological Thought*, 10(1). 138-154. DOI:10.5964/psyc.v10i1.184.
- Alimoradi, M., Asadi, H., Asadbeigy, H., & Asadniya, R. (2014). The effects of emotional intelligence on reduction of aggressive behaviors in juvenile with speech impairment. *International Journal of Basic Sciences and Applied Research*, 03(1), 265-269.
- Anwar, P. (2016). *2 Siswa SMP di Pekanbaru duel hanya karena saling pandang, satu tewas*. Diakses dari <https://m.detik.com/news/berita/d-3310715/2-siswa-smp-di-pekanbaru-duel-hanya-karena-saling-pandang-satu-tewas>. Pada tanggal 17 Juli 2019.
- Bibi, A. Saleem, M. Khalid, A. dan Safique, N. (2019). Emotional intelligence and aggression among university students of Pakistan: A Correlational Study. *Journal of Aggression, Maltreatment & Trauma*, 6(1) 121-311. DOI:org/10.1080/10926771.2019.1709592
- Budi, T. (2019). *Terlibat tawuran, seorang pelajar SMK tewas di bacok*. Diakses dari <https://news.okezone.com/read/2019/02/02/512/2012750/terlibat-tawuran-seorang-pelajar-smk-tewas-dibacok>. Pada tanggal 17 Juli 2019.
- Buss, A. H. & Perry, M. (1992). The aggression questionnaire. *Journal of personality and social psychology*. The American psychological Association, Inc. 12(2), 98-97.
- Buss, A. H. (2001). *Personality: evolutionary heritage and human distinctiveness*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of Research Writing and Uses of Research Methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Einstein, E. & Indrawati, E. (2016). Hubungan antara pola asuh otoriter orang tua dengan perilaku agresif siswa/i sudy karya Magelang. *Jurnal Empati. Universitas Diponegoro*. 5(3), 491-502.
- Goleman. (1996). *Emotional intelligence*. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Hurlock B. E. (1994). *Psikologi perkembangan suatu pendekatan sepanjang rentang kehidupan*. Jakarta: Erlangga.

- Kaya, H. Hazar, B. Beyleroglu, M. Sari, I. & Yilmaz, A. (2017). Relationship between emosional intelligence and agression on boxers. *Future Human Image*.8(1), 121-132.
- Masud, H. Ahmad, M. & Cho, K. (2019). Parenting styles and aggression among young adolescents: a systematic review of literature. *Community Mental Health Journal*. DOI: org/10.1007/s10597-019-00400-0.
- Luthfiani, D. (2017). Hubungan antarakecerdasan emosional dengan perilaku agresif siswa kelas VIII 8 Kediri tahun ajaran 2017/2018. *Jurnal Simki-Pedagogia* 02(1), 98-101.
- Masoumeh, H., Mansor, M., Yaacob, S., Talib, M., & Sara, M. (2014). Emotional intelligence and aggression among adolescents in Tehran, Iran. *Life Science Journal*, 11(5), 506-511.
- Moghaddam, M., Asli, F., & Taravatmanesh, S. (2016). The relationship between parenting styles and aggression in adolescents of Zahedan City in 2014. *Shiraz E- Med*. 17(7-8). 485-515. DOI:10.17795/semj38515.
- Robbinson, C. Mandleco, B. Roper, S. & Hart, C. (1995). *The Parenting Styles and Dimensions Questionnaire (PSDQ)*. *Bringham Young University Psychological Reports*, 1995, 819-830.
- Salovey, P & Mayer, J. (1990). *Emotional intelligence, imagination, cognition, and personality*. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Santrock. (2002). *Life span development (perkembangan masa hidup)*. Jilid 1: Edisi Kelima. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Sarwono. (2003). *Psikologi remaja*. Jakarta: PT Raja Gravido Persada.
- Papalia, Olds, dan Feldman (2007). *Human development*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- Prasyatiani. (2013). *Agresivitas mahasiswa dalam demonstrasi*. Diakses dari <https://www.kompasiana.com/penapsikologi/55202207a333119644b65a06/agresivitas-mahasiswa-dalam-demonstrasi>. Pada bulan November 2020.
- Yusuf, S. (2011). *Psikologi perkembangan anak dan remaja*. Bandung: PT. Simbiosis Rekatama Media.